

Short communication

First verified record of genus *Onesia* (Diptera: Calliphoridae) from India

Meenakshi Bharti

Department of Zoology and Environmental Sciences, Punjabi University, Patiala, Punjab, India.

(Email: adubharti@gmail.com)

Keywords: *Diptera, Calliphoridae, Genus Onesia, new record, India.*

Received: 14 August 2018; Revised: 2 September 2018; Online: 12 September 2018.

Generic group *Onesia* of subfamily Calliphorinae (family Calliphoridae) is an assemblage of species of genera *Bellardia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863, *Onesia* Robineau Desvoidy, 1830, *Polleniopsis* Townsend, 1917, *Tainanina* Villeneuve, 1927 and *Tricycleopsis* Villeneuve, 1927. So far, from India the group is only represented by species of *Bellardia*, *Polleniopsis* and *Tainanina* (Verves, 2005; Bharti, 2015; Bharti & Verves, 2016). The present study herein reports the first verified record of genus *Onesia* from India.

Genus *Onesia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 is represented by 61 species from the World, with 28 Palearctic, 23 Australasian/Oceanian, 7 Oriental, while two are common to Palearctic and Oriental regions, and one to Australasian and Oriental regions (Rognes, 1991, 1997, 1998; Schumann 1964, 1974, 1986; Verves, 2004, 2005; Verves & Khrokalo 2006; Xue *et al.*, 2006). *Onesia* flies are viviparous and the larvae are thought to be parasites or predators of earthworms or snails (Schumann, 1964), however these type of associations are yet to be verified (Rognes, 1991). The species in question, *Onesia atripalpis* (Malloch, 1935) was earlier recorded from Malaysia and Philippines and during the present study it has been collected from western Himalaya (Nanda Devi and Valley of flowers National Park, Uttarakhand, India) at an altitude of 3500m. Notably, the park is an abode to numerous endemic species of plants and animals and is recognised as World Heritage Site by UNESCO.

Figures 1-2: *Onesia atripalpis*: 1. Head front view; 2. Profile

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance rendered by Department of Science and Technology, Ministry of Science and Technology, New Delhi, vide Project No. SR/WOS-A/LS-109/2016(G), is gratefully acknowledged.

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